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Research Article

ALTERATIONS IN THE SERUM LIPOPROTEINS OF PRIMI-PAROUS FEMALES SUFFERING FROM ECLAMPSIA AND ITS COMPARISON WITH NORMAL PREGNANT FEMALES¹Dr Afeen Malik, ²Dr Maida Hassan, ³Dr Alishba Saeed¹Mohi Ud Din Islamic Medical College, AJK²Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College³Mayo Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Objective: To assess the alterations in the serum lipoproteins in primi-parous females suffering from eclampsia and its comparison with the normal healthy females having pregnancy.

Methodology: This transverse research work carried out on 65 Primi-parous patients of eclampsia and 21 pregnant females with normal blood pressure in the Mayo Hospital, Lahore. The record of the history of every female was maintained on well-organized questionnaire. Utilization of standard methods carried out for the measurement of the BP (Blood Pressure). We collected a blood sample of five milliliter from every participant to examine the level of serum lipoproteins. SPSS V.20 was in use for the statistical analysis of the selected information. P value <0.050 was statistically significant.

Results: Average age of hypertensive females was 23.20 ± 0.52 years whereas average age of the healthy controls was 23.90 ± 1.16 years. We found a significant difference in the level of lipoproteins. Women present with eclampsia had 28.80%, 29.50%, 31.10%, 32.90% and 65.30% high LDL-C (Low density Lipoprotein-Cholesterol), TG (Triglycerides), ratio between TC (Total Cholesterol) and HDL-C (High Density Lipoprotein-Cholesterol), ratio of LDL-C to HDL-C and ratio of TG and HDL-C correspondingly as compared to the group of healthy controls. The concentrations of HDL-C, ratio between HDL-C and VLDL-C and level of apolipoprotein A-1 were 26.90%, 56.60% and 27.90% respectively, less in the group of patients as compared to the group of healthy controls.

Conclusion: The findings of this research work shows that assessment of the concentration of serum lipoprotein in the duration of antenatal period can be beneficial in early identification and prevention of the development of eclampsia.

KEY WORDS: Primi-Parous, Pregnancy, Assessment, Alterations, Pressure, Eclampsia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Eclampsia is very complicate multi-system hypertensive abnormality present in whole world in the duration of late pregnancy. This complication is also a leading cause of high rate of morbidity of mothers as well as fetal [1]. Eclampsia has a sudden onset; therefore, it is a dangerous anomaly in pregnancy. This complication has the features for the development of the colonic seizures in persons already suffering from preeclampsia. Risk of the development of the PIH (Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension) increases with increase in age [2]. This complication has association with the dysfunction and hypoxia of placenta [3]. It characterization carried out by BP of 140/90 mmHg or increase in SBP (Systolic Blood Pressure) of greater than 30.0 mmHg or DBP of greater than 15.0 mmHg after complete twenty gestational weeks along with proteinuria $\geq$ 300.0mg per 24 hours or higher or equal to 1+ or 100.0 mg /dl by dipstick response [4, 5]. Preeclampsia normally occurs in the period of 2nd or 3rd trimester of pregnancy and this problem is more frequent with the 1st pregnancy of females in nulliparous. About 7.0% to 10.0% pregnancy are complicated by pregnancy induced hypertension in the countries which are under-development [6]. The rate of incidence of PIH in India is 15.20%, and this incidence is 4 times greater in the nulliparous females as compared to the in multipara [7]. In Berhampur, maternal mortalities because of PIH was 32.0% which is two time greater than the rate of incidence present in India [8, 9].

In country of Nigeria, rate of prevalence is high in the North regions of country with incidence rate of 17.0% and it is responsible for 40.0% maternal mortalities. Most of the affected are the females of teenage because of early marriages in that country. In our country Pakistan, the rate of incidence of eclampsia is about 19.0%. A research work performed in Peshawar, Pakistan stated the rate of maternal mortality because of eclampsia as 16.70% that accounted for 29.40% of total maternal mortalities in the duration of one-year period. Some works documented the alterations in the level of lipoproteins in hypertension [12]. There is increase in the serum lipids in the period of pregnancy and it is elevated 2 times in PIH [13]. Abnormal concentrations of lipoprotein are accountable for damages to endothelium which can lead to high BP as well as proteinuria and these two are vital signs of pregnancy induced hypertension [14]. The alterations in the concentration of lipoproteins cause damages to endothelium, atherosclerosis and other diseases of heart. Main sign of PIH is the HTN (Hypertension), this is because of the vasospastic incidents in uterus, brain and placenta [15]. This

research work carried out to provide the comparison between the alterations in the serum lipoprotein of healthy pregnant females and primi-parous females suffering from eclampsia.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out on the pregnant females who got admission in the Gynecology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore. There were 86 females with pregnancy comprising 21 normotensive Primi-parous females and 65 primi-parous females suffering from eclampsia at age of gestation of greater than 20 weeks in this research work. We took the written consent from the participants of this research work after explaining them the purpose of this research work. Ethical committee of the institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. Females from both groups present with history of DM (Diabetes Mellitus), HTN (Hypertension), renal diseases, disorders of liver, multiple pregnancies, females with history of eclampsia in their family and history of utilization of various drugs influencing the lipid levels for treatment got exclusion from this research work.

We included the primi-parous pregnant females of eclampsia with gestational age of greater than twenty weeks. The diagnosis of the patients of eclampsia carried out with the presence of persistent HTN (140.0/90.0 mmHg or higher), proteinuria (identified by the heat test of urine) without or with edema. We collected the history of every patient and used standard methods for the measurement of blood pressure of every patient. We obtained the five-milliliter blood from every participant of both groups. We transferred all the specimens on ice cubes for further investigation in the research laboratory of the institute. The measurement of serum TG and TC carried out with the utilization of enzymatic method of Elitech diagnostic kits made up of France. The measurement of serum HDL-C carried out with the utilization of the Merck Diagnostics kits made up of Germany. We used the T-test for the determination of statistical significance. SPSS V. 20 was in use for the statistical analysis of collected information. We presented the results in averages and standard deviations.

RESULTS:

Average age and mean gestational age of the pregnant females in both groups were comparable. SBP and DBP of group of patients was much increased and it was much significant when compared with the group of controls (Table-1).

Table-I: Comparison of Different Variables of Primiparous Pregnant Women with The Control Group

Variables Mean±SEM	Patients Mean±SEM	Control Mean±SEM	P
Age (years)	23.15± 0.52	23.90± 1.16	NS
Gestation age (weeks)	31.64 ± 0.58	30.81± 1.03	NS
Systolic BP (mmHg)	158.79 ± 2.82	115.23± 2.05	0.001
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	105.59 ± 2.02	76.04± 1.54	0.001

Average levels of blood lipid in the females with normal pregnancy and in primi-parous females suffering from eclampsia are available in Table-2. There were significant differences available in serum HDL-C ($P<0.0010$), VLDL-C ($P<0.0010$), TG ($P<0.0010$), TC and HDL-C ratio ($P<0.0010$), serum TG and HDL-C ratio ($P<0.0010$), ratio of HDL-C and VLDL-C ($P<0.010$) and level of apolipoprotein A1 ($P<0.0010$) among both groups. But we found significant disparity ($P>0.050$) in TC, LDL-C, level of apolipoprotein B-100, ratio of LDL to apolipoprotein B-100 and ratio of HDL and level of apolipoprotein A-1 in the patients suffering from eclampsia and healthy females with pregnancy. Females suffering from eclampsia were present with 28.80%, 29.50%, 31.10%, 32.90% and 65.30% high LDL-C, TG, ratio of TC and HDL-C, ratio of LDL-C and HDL-C and ratio of TG and HDL-C respectively in comparison with the group of healthy pregnant females. The concentrations of HDL-C, ratio of HDL-C and VLDL-C and level of apolipoprotein A-1 were 26.90%, 56.60% and 27.90% respectively, low in the group of patients as compared to their healthy controls.

Table-II: Comparison of Lipoprotein Concentrations in Primiparous Women with Eclampsia and Normal Pregnancy

Parameters	Eclampsia group Mean ± SEM	Control group Mean ± SEM	% deviation from control	P value
Total Chol. (mg/dL)	213.61 ± 6.84	206.28 ± 16.47	3.6 ↑	NS
HDL-Chol. (mg/dL)	40.72 ± 1.16	53.20 ± 2.36	23.5 ↓	0.001
LDL-Chol. (mg/dL)	109.55 ± 6.37	106.55 ± 14.37	2.8 ↑	NS
VLDL-Chol. (mg/dL)	65.12 ± 3.51	44.7 ± 3.57	45.7 ↑	0.001
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	327.98 ± 17.78	223.4 ± 17.87	46.8 ↑	0.001
APO-A1 (mg/dL)	143.59 ± 5.85	189 ± 11.31	24.0 ↓	0.001
APO-B100 (mg/dL)	118.98 ± 4.96	126.18 ± 3.25	5.70 ↓	NS
TC: HDL-C ratio	5.38 ± 0.19	3.95 ± 0.36	36.2 ↓	0.001
LDL-C: HDL-C ratio	2.76 ± 0.16	2.07 ± 0.29	33.3 ↑	0.01
TG: HDL-C ratio	8.38 ± 0.50	4.41 ± 0.43	90.0 ↑	0.001
HDL-C: VLDL-C ratio	0.72 ± 0.03	1.30 ± 0.09	44.6 ↓	0.001
LDL: APO-B100	0.99 ± 0.06	0.95 ± 0.14	4.2 ↑	NS
HDL: APO-A1	0.31 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.03	10.7 ↑	NS

DISCUSSION:

Rise of the serum lipids in the duration of pregnancy period and hypertension induced by pregnancy have been stated in many research works [16, 17]. Remarkably great alterations have been recorded in the TG, which may go as high as 2 to 3 times in last three months of pregnancy period [18]. We noticed the same pattern in this current research work where a significant increase in serum TG was noticed in eclampsia patients when its comparison carried out with females having normal pregnancy. The hyperoestrogenemic pregnancy state is mainly

accountable for this increase in the level of TG in the period of pregnancy. Estrogen is the cause of induction of hepatic bio-synthesis of endogenous TG which is carried by the VLDL [19]. Enhanced level of TG, discovered in pregnancy induced HTN [20] is expected to be deposited in susceptible vessels, like the spiral arteries of uterine and contribute to the dysfunction of endothelium, through the creation of small and dense LDL. Mohanty [21] in his research study, discovered a significant rise in the cholesterol of serum in toxemia of pregnancy in primi-parous pregnant

females. The results of current research work are contrary to mentioned outcomes where concentration of cholesterol increased up to certain amount but no significant change in the level of total cholesterol was examined. These findings of current research work are consistent with the results of other stated research studies [20, 22]. In the current research work, the average level of HDL-C was approximately 24.0% low in the patients suffering from eclampsia as compared to the females having normal pregnancy ($P < 0.0010$). Some other research works also reported the similar findings [23, 24].

In current research work, change in the LDL-C was not much significant in the participants of both groups but the levels of serum VLDL-C increased significantly ($P < 0.0010$) in pregnant females suffering from eclampsia, which may be because of the hyper-triglyceridemia causing increase entry of VLDL that carries the endogenous TG into the circulation. The levels of VLDL-C as reported by some other research works [25] might increase to 2.50 folds at term over the level before pregnancy. Level of VLDL further increase in case of eclampsia as discovered in this current research work and as stated by some other research works [20, 26]. In this current research work, the concentration of APO B-100 reduced in the group of patients but it was not much significant. There was a significant reduction was recorded in the ratio between HDL-C & VLDL-C in the group of pregnant females suffering from eclampsia as compared to the pregnant females with normal pregnancy. These findings of current research work are comparable with the results of one other research study conducted by Enquobahrie [27]. There is not recognition yet about the significance of these ratios in the duration of pregnancy and prevalence of eclampsia, however, we cannot ignore the significance of changed ratio of serum lipids as these ratios point to some additional risks in the patients of eclampsia with pregnancy.

CONCLUSION:

Results of this research work concluded that evaluation of the concentration of lipoproteins in the females in their pregnancy period is much important to prevent the development of eclampsia.

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